

Investigation of Psychological Resilience Effect on Emotional Eating; Hotel Employees Sample

Psikolojik Dayanıklılığın Duygusal Yemeye Etkisi; Otel Çalışanları Örneği

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Abstract

Negative emotions effect to psychology and lead to eating disorders. Emotional eating occurs in response to negative emotional states. Hotel employees who have high workload and stress levels they are constantly exposed to food as part of their work processes. The research aims to measure the effect of hotel employees' psychological resilience on emotional eating behavior. The survey method was used in the study. The preliminary research was conducted with 200 participants and the final research with 410 participants. Participants were selected from individuals who working different departments of four-star and five-star hotels in Istanbul. Data were analyzed with regression analyses. As a result, it was found that self-perception, future perception, and social resources, which are the sub-dimensions of psychological resilience, had a statistically significant and negative effect on emotional eating. Also, no statistically significant effect of family cohesion and social competence, which are the other sub-dimensions of psychological resilience, on emotional eating was detected. The research is expected to contribute theoretically to the interdisciplinary literature in the fields of tourism, gastronomy, nutrition and psychology. In addition, practical contributions to hotel sector employees in terms of physiological and psychological aspects are aimed.

Keywords: Eating Disorders, Emotional Eating, Psychological Resilience, Hotel Employees.

Özet

Olumsuz duygu durumları psikolojiyi etkileyerek yeme bozukluklarına yol açmaktadır. Duygusal yeme, olumsuz duygu durumlarına tepki olarak ortaya çıkan bir yeme bozukluğudur. İş yükü ve stres düzeyi yüksek olan otel çalışanları iş süreçleri kapsamında sürekli olarak yemeğe maruz kalan bireylerdir. Araştırma, otel çalışanlarının psikolojik dayanıklılıklarının duygusal yeme üzerindeki etkisini ölçmeyi amaçlamaktadır. Çalışmada nicel yöntemlerden yararlanılmıştır. Veriler anket yöntemi ile toplanmıştır. Ön araştırma 200, nihai araştırma 410 katılımcıyla gerçekleştirilmiştir. Katılımcılar İstanbul'daki dört ve beş yıldızlı otellerin farklı departmanlarında çalışan bireyler arasından seçilmiştir. Veriler regresyon analizleri ile analiz edilmiştir. Araştırma sonucunda psikolojik dayanıklılığın alt boyutları olan benlik algısı, gelecek algısı ve sosyal kaynakların duygusal yeme üzerinde istatistiksel olarak anlamlı ve negatif bir etkiye sahip olduğu tespit edilmiştir. Aynı zamanda psikolojik dayanıklılığın alt boyutları olan aile uyumu ve sosyal yeterliliğin duygusal yeme üzerinde istatistiksel olarak anlamlı bir etkisi saptanamamıştır. Araştırmanın turizm, gastronomi, beslenme ve psikoloji alanındaki disiplinler arası literatüre teorik açıdan katkı sağlaması beklenmektedir. Ayrıca, otel sektörü çalışanlarına fizyolojik ve psikolojik açıdan pratik katkılar hedeflenmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Yeme Bozuklukları, Duygusal Yeme, Psikolojik Dayanıklılık, Otel Çalışanları

Introduction

The eating phenomenon is related to many different factors, including psychological factors (Enriquez & Archila-Godinez, 2022; Simone et al., 2021; Van Den Berg et al., 2019). On the other hand, the fact that eating disorders are among the most prominent factors that negatively affect the health of individuals (Himmerich, 2021; O'Brien et al., 2017) has caused the problem to be studied from many different perspectives, including psychology. Numerous studies define eating disorders and investigate their causes in literature (Saha et al., 2022; Streatfeild et al., 2021; Li et al., 2020).

Individuals may acquire eating disorders due to psychological factors and tend to consume high-calorie, harmful foods during times of frustration and depression (Badri et al., 2021). Also, individuals with atypical depression may have weight gain (Schaffer et al., 2022; Barchiesi et al., 2016). Studies have shown that individuals tend to consume more carbohydrates while facing psychological issues, while obese people often eat to alleviate discomfort and tension (Daneshzad et al., 2020; Gallagher et al., 2019). Along with all these, emotional eating is revealed as a result of psychological factors.

The hotel industry affects the psychology of employees with intense and stressful work processes. Many studies reveal that intense and long working hours negatively affect the psychology of hotel employees (Kalargyrou et al., 2023; Haddoud et al., 2022; Ross, 2017) and emphasize the importance of psychological resilience for hotel employees (Anasori et al., 2023; Yucel et al., 2021). In addition, access or exposure to food in the hotel is extremely high and leads to eating disorders (Okumus et al., 2019; Kim et al., 2016). There are very limited studies investigating the emotional eating or eating disorders of hotel employees (Okumus et al., 2022) and no study investigating the relationship between emotional eating and psychological resilience in the hotel sector. In addition, even though several studies focus on eating disorders within the scope of psychological factors and resilience (Chang et al., 2021; Isaksson et al., 2021; Coleman & Caswell, 2020), studies investigating the effect of psychological resilience on emotional eating were very limited in the literature.

The study aims to examine the effect of psychological resilience on emotional eating in the context of hotel employees. The regression analyses were used in the study. The research aims to make theoretical contributions to interdisciplinary literature in the field of tourism gastronomy, nutrition and psychology. In addition, practical contributions are aimed to improve the physiological and psychological health status of hotel employees and to the development of human resources in the tourism industry as well as hotel sector.

Literature

Psychological Resilience

Psychological resilience is an individual's ability to cope with negative situations such as various obstacles, stress, disappointment, and sadness encountered in the life process. In this context, it refers to the ability to adapt to challenging conditions in life (Sisto et al., 2019). If the psychological resilience of the individual is addressed comprehensively and in a way that is not independent of the environmental factors, it is seen that the factors of perception of self, perception of the future, structured style, family cohesion, social competence, and social resources emerge (Friborg et al., 2003). Perception of self, perception of future, structural style, and social competence are individual characteristics related to resilience. Perception of self is the ability of individuals to direct their future by learning lessons from the events they have experienced before. Individuals assess and adjust their behaviors and relationships in response to bad results stemming from the relationships formed throughout their lives (Cazan & Dumitrescu, 2016). Perception of the future is how individuals guide their present actions and thoughts according to their future intentions. People with a strong sense of long-term perception can demonstrate intentional and deliberate actions toward achieving their future goals (Kooji et al., 2018). Structural style is connected to an individual's personality, self-assurance, capabilities, and self-control. The capacity to plan, organize, and analyze one's daily responsibilities is defined as social competency (Friborg et al., 2005). Social competency is the ability of individuals to rely on their skills. It was detected that individuals with high social competence are more determined to solve events because they believe in their abilities (Taborsky & Oliveira, 2012).

Social resources are interactions in social life that influence psychological resilience as an environmental component. The social environment has effects such as changing negative conditions for individuals or reducing their degree of importance (Kılınc & Sis Celik, 2021). Family cohesion elucidates the collaboration among family members during challenging circumstances (Mohd-Zaharim & Hashim, 2023).

Emotional Eating

Eating is a biological necessity for survival, but it is also intertwined with psychology (Himmerich et al., 2021). Emotions like stress, anxiety, and anger can lead to overeating beyond what is required for basic sustenance (Linardon et al., 2021). In this context, food intake with more calories than the daily energy requirement leads to unbalanced nutrition and health problems (Stewart et al., 2022).

Emotional eating occurs as a reaction to individu-

als' negative emotional states and affects healthy eating habits (Konttinen, 2020). People may engage in overeating due to several factors when experiencing bad emotions. Various ideas, including the escape theory, limitation theory, and internal-external obesity theory, have been proposed to explain why individuals engage in overeating when experiencing negative emotional states (Sevincer & Konuk, 2013). Individuals exhibit overeating behavior in this context as a means to avoid negative emotional states, the pressure to control their eating habits, or external stimuli in the environment rather than internal factors like hunger and energy requirements (Wang et al., 2023). Additionally, it has been observed that individuals with emotional eating behaviors eat outside of main meals and late at night and prefer unhealthy foods. People who engage in emotional eating tend to favor unhealthy foods that are rich in carbohydrates, fat, and sugar (Kaur et al., 2022). The fact that these high-calorie and unhealthy food types are consumed with overeating behavior in negative emotional states constitutes the research problem.

Psychological Resilience, Eating Disorders, and Emotional Eating

The relationship between eating disorders and psychological factors was discussed in many studies (Isaksson et al., 2021; Coleman & Caswell, 2020). Nishimi and his colleagues (2022), found that psychological resilience negatively effected eating disorders and weight gain, Süss and friends (2020), found that psychological resilience positively effects the diet quality of individuals. Milligan and her colleagues (2024), have shown that eating control can be achieved by increasing psychological resilience while Las Hayas and friends (2016), identified the relationship between emotional eating and the variables of active coping, increasing well-being, initiating new projects, and receiving social support associated with eating disorders and psychological resilience. However, there are very limited studies investigating the relationship between psychological resilience and emotional eating in the literature. Robert and his colleagues (2022), found that psychological resilience negatively effects emotional eating in their study on adults in France, and Spinosa and friends (2019), found that psychological resilience may have a partial effect on emotional eating by effecting coping with stress. Considering all these studies, 6 hypotheses were determined in the research.

- H1:** As perception of self increases, emotional eating decreases.
- H2:** As perception of the future increases, emotional eating decreases.
- H3:** As structured style increases, emotional eating decreases.
- H4:** As family cohesion increases, emotional eating

decreases.

H5: As social competence increases, emotional eating decreases.

H6: As social resources increase, emotional eating decreases.

Methodology

The study aims to analyze the effect of psychological resilience on emotional eating. Six hypotheses were formulated to align with the study's purpose. The model for the hypotheses is presented in Figure 1. The study data were collected by the survey method.

Figure 1. Research Model

Sample

The population of the study is hotel employees. The sample consisted of 610 participants working in four-star and five-star hotels in Istanbul. Participants were selected from individuals working in different departments, such as the front office, reception, housekeeping, kitchen, service personnel, and administrative departments. Considering that Istanbul benefits the tourism industry, especially in the context of hotels, the sample was selected among hotel employees in this city (Yozcu, 2017). Also, work stress and psychological wear are high for the employees of four-star and five-star hotels in Istanbul (Arslan et al., 2023) and employees may be individuals from different countries of the world (Celik, 2023). For the preliminary research, data were collected from 200 people working in different departments of the hotels. For the final phase, data were collected from 103 participants working in the front office and reception department, 100 in housekeeping, 104 in the kitchen and service department, and 103 in administrative departments. Data were collected upon the decision of the Anadolu University Ethics Commission dated 28.02.2023 with protocol number 488278. Preliminary research data were collected between May 20, 2023, and June 28, 2023, and final research data were collected between July and September 27, 2023.

Scale

"The Resilience Scale for Adults" developed by Friberg et al. (2005), which was adapted into Turkish (Basim & Cetin, 2011), and "Dutch Eating Behavior Questionnaire (DEBQ)" (Van Strien et al., 1986), whose reliability and validity for Turkey was tested in 2011 (Bozan et al., 2011) were used to collect the study data. The study questionnaire included all dimensions (self-perception, future perception, structural style, social competence, social resources, and family cohesion) and sub-items of "The Resilience Scale for Adults" and the emotional eating sub-dimension and items of the DEBQ Questionnaire to measure psychological resilience. The questionnaire in this context comprised 46 questions, with 33 focusing on psychological resilience and 13 on emotional eating behavior. The questionnaire was employed in the preliminary study process. As a result of the Cronbach alpha test and factor analysis of the preliminary research, all items related to the structured style dimension (four items), three items related to the family cohesion dimension, one item related to the social competence dimension, and three items related to the social resources dimension were removed from the preliminary questionnaire, and the final questionnaire was created. The final questionnaire consisted of six items on perception of style, four items on perception of the future, three items on family cohesion, five items on social competence, four items on social resources, and 13 items on emotional eating.

Data analysis

The Kaiser-Meier-Olkin Test was first applied to the preliminary and final research data, and then the Cronbach Alpha test and factor analysis were performed to measure reliability and validity. After the reliability and validity of the final research data were determined by Cronbach's Alpha test and factor analysis, the normality test was used to determine whether the data were normally distributed. Following the normality test, the study hypotheses were assessed with regression analysis. Additionally, frequency analysis was conducted.

Findings and Interpretation

Preliminary research results

The Kaiser-Meier-Olkin (KMO) test was first performed on the preliminary research data, and the test result was calculated as 0.854. Following the KMO test, the Cronbach Alpha test and factor analysis were conducted to determine the reliability and validity of the scale. The test revealed that the Cronbach Alpha value of all dimensions of the scale except the structured style dimension was above 0.60 and was found to be reliable. The results of the Cronbach

Alpha test for the preliminary research are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Cronbach Alpha Results of Preliminary Survey

Dimensions	Cronbach alpha
Perception of self	0.707
Structured style	-0.269
Perception of future	0.802
Family cohesion	0.767
Social competence	0.686
Social resources	0.708
Emotional eating	0.932

Considering the reliability analysis of the preliminary research, the structured style dimension in the scale was removed from the scale. Also, factor analysis revealed that seven items with insufficient factor loadings. These items removed from the scale are three items related to the family cohesion dimension, one item related to the social competence dimension, and three items related to the social resources dimension. Following this process, the questionnaire was reorganized, and the final research was conducted.

Research Results

Frequency analysis results

Frequency analysis was conducted to determine the demographic information, departments, and length of service of the participants.

Table 2. Frequency Analysis Results

Sex	F	%	Having children	F	%
Female	239	58.3	Yes	172	42
Male	171	41.7	No	238	58
Total	410	100	Total	410	100
Age	F	%	Department	F	%
20-35	224	54.6	Housekeeping	100	24.4
36-45	144	35.1	Kitchen& Food and Beverage Service	104	25.4
46-60	34	8.3	Front Office	103	25.1
61+	8	2.0	Others	103	25.1
Total	410	100	Total	410	100
Marital status	F	%	Income	F	%
Married	236	57.6	0-15000 TRY	136	33.15
Celibate	174	42.4	15001 TRY -25000 TRY	186	45.35
Total	410	100	25001 + TRY	88	21.5
Working year	F	%	Total	410	100
0-5	118	28.8			
6-10	144	35.1			
11-20	95	23.2			
21-25	38	9.3			
26+	15	3.7			
Total	410	100			

As can be seen in Table 2, 239 of the participants were female and 171 were male. More than 50% of the participants are between the ages of 20 and 35 and single with no children. 100 participants work in housekeeping, 103 in the front office, 104 in food and beverage, and 103 in administrative departments such as human resources, accounting, and finance. 78.5% of the participants have an income of TRY 25000 and below. More than 70% of the participants have more than five years of working experience in the hotel.

Reliability and validity

The Kaiser-Meier-Olkin (KMO) test was first performed on the final research data, and the test result was calculated as 0.862. Following the KMO test, the Cronbach Alpha test and factor analysis were conducted to determine the reliability and validity of the scale. Cronbach Alpha values of all dimensions of the scale were higher than 0.70. Considering

the Cronbach Alpha values, it can be said that scale items are consistent with each other, represent dimensions and the scale is quite reliable (Kline, 2000). The factor loadings of the items related to the dimensions were higher than 0.50. Cronbach's alpha test results for the dimensions of the scale were presented in Table 3. The items and factor loadings for the dimensions were presented in Table 4.

Table 3. Scale Dimensions and Cronbach Alpha Values

Dimensions	Cronbach alpha
Perception of self	0.858
Perception of future	0.881
Family cohesion	0.900
Social competence	0.745
Social resources	0.844
Emotional eating	0.940
Emotional eating	0.932

Table 4. Factor Analysis Results

Item no	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	0.825					
2	0.730					
3	0.698					
4	0.783					
5	0.787					
6	0.669					
7		0.712				
8		0.803				
9		0.788				
10		0.805				
11			0.851			
12			0.894			
13			0.891			
14				0.623		
15				0.542		
16				0.755		
17				0.657		
18				0.807		
19					0.855	
20					0.883	
21					0.861	
22					0.505	
23						0.633
24						0.600
25						0.839
26						0.731
27						0.841
28						0.824
29						0.741
30						0.793
31						0.750
32						0.758
33						0.770
34						0.775
35						0.800

Regression analysis results

The skewness and kurtosis values for the items were taken as references to determine whether the data were normally distributed before the hypothesis testing. The skewness and kurtosis values of all items related to the scale were found to be in the range of +3 to -3. The regression analysis revealed that the independent variables, perception of self, per-

ception of the future, and social resources, significantly predicted the dependent variable, emotional eating. The model that family cohesion and social competence independent variables effect emotional eating dependent variables was not statistically significant (H4 and H5 were rejected). The relevant parameters are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Regression Analysis Results

Independent variable	Dependent variable	B	Std. error	(b)	t	P	R	R2	F	P
Perception of self	Emotional eating	-0.241	0.059	-0.197	-4.057	0.001	0.197a	0.039	16.459	0.001b
Perception of future	Emotional eating	-0.152	0.044	-0.170	-3.485	0.001	0.170a	0.029	12.146	0.001b
Social resources	Emotional eating	-0.156	0.049	-0.157	-3.211	0.001	0.157a	0.025	10.308	0.001b

Considering the regression analysis results in Table 5, the models are significant (for the perception of self, F: 16.459, p: 0.001 for the perception of self, F: 12.146 p: 0.001 for the perception of the future, F: 10.308 p: 0.001). Furthermore, while perception of self increases, emotional eating decreases (B:-0.241, p:0.001) (H1 accepted). 3.9% of emotional eating behavior can be explained by the perception of self (R2: 0.039). While the perception of the future variable increases, the emotional eating variable decreases (B:-0.152, p:0.001). (H2 accepted). 2.9% of emotional eating behavior can be explained by the perception of the future (R2:0.029). While the social

resources variable increases, the emotional eating variable decreases (B:-0.156, p:0.001) (H6 accepted). 2.5% of emotional eating behavior can be explained by the social resources variable (R2:0.025).

T-test and ANOVA results

In the study, also t-test and ANOVA were made. A t-test was made to examine whether the variables related to psychological resilience and the emotional eating variable differed statistically according to gender and marital status variables. The T-test results are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. T-test Results

	Levene's test	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. 2
Perception of future	Equal variances assumed	5.029	.025	2.076	408	.038
	Equal variances not assumed			2.043	378.821	.042
	Marital status	N	Mean	Std.	Mean difference	Std. Error difference
	Married	236	3.7998	.98683	.21502	.10355
	Celibate	174	3.5848	1.09995	.21502	.10526

Emotional eating	Levene's test	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. 2
	Equal variances assumed	3.821	.051	-2.020	408	.044
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.988	349.876	.048
	Marital status	N	Mean	Std.	Mean difference	Std. Error difference
	Married	236	2.1721	.88359	-.18688	.09252
Celibate	174	2.3590	.98041	-.18688	.09398	

As can be seen in Table 6, there is a significant difference between the perception of the future of the married and celibate participants (Sig. 2: 0.42). Married participants have a higher perception of the future (Mean: 3.7998) than single participants (Mean: 3.5848). Also, there is a significant difference between the emotional eating of the married and celibate participants (Sig. 2: 0.44). Single participants had a

higher rate of emotional eating (Mean: 2.3590) than married participants (Mean: 2.1721).

ANOVA test was made to examine whether the variables related to psychological resilience and the emotional eating variable differed statistically according to age, income, having children, working year, and department. ANOVA results are presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Anova Test Results

Perception of self	Tukey HSD	F	F	Mean
		0-15000 TRY	15001 TRY-25000 TRY	.11397
			25001 + TRY	.28443*
		15001 TRY-25000 TRY	0-15000 TRY	-.1139
	25001 + TRY		-.17045	
	25001 + TRY	0-15000 TRY	-.28443*	
		15001 TRY-25000 TRY	-.17045	
	F	N	Mean	Std.
	0-15000 TRY	136	4.1140	.70527
	15001 TRY-25000 TRY	186	4.0000	.72348
25001 + TRY	88	3.8295	.88624	
Total	410	4.0012	.76064	

Family cohesion	Tukey HSD	F	F	Mean
		0-15000 TRY	15001 TRY-25000 TRY	.43461*
			25001 + TRY	.35495
		15001 TRY-25000 TRY	0-15000 TRY	-.43461*
			25001 + TRY	-.07967
		25001 + TRY	0-15000 TRY	-.35495
	15001 TRY-25000 TRY		.07967	
	F	N	Mean	Std.
	0-15000 TRY	136	3.2034	1.35183
	15001 TRY-25000 TRY	186	2.7688	1.35246
25001 + TRY	88	2.8485	1.29041	
Total	410	2.9301	1.35013	

As can be seen in Table 7, there was a statistically significant difference between the perception of self of participants who had 0-15000 TRY and 25001 TRY monthly income. As a result of the Tukey test (Sig.023), it was determined that the self-perception of the participants who had 15000 TRY and below monthly income (Mean: 4.1140) was higher than the participants who had 25001 TRY and above (Sig: .017, Mean: 3.8295). Additionally, there was a statistically significant difference between the family cohesion of participants who had 0-15000 TRY and 15001 TRY- 25001 TRY monthly income. As a result of the Tukey test (Sig.014), the family cohesion of the participants who had an income of 15000 TRY and below (Sig: .012, Mean: 3.2034) was higher than the participants 25000 and above (Mean: 2.8485).

positively effects eating disorders (Arroyo & Segrin, 2013). In addition to hypothesis tests, the relationship between variables and demographic variables was investigated in the study. It was determined that married individuals' emotional eating is lower but perception of future is higher than single. The findings are line with studies that found that married individuals have more motivation to stop eating for psychological reasons (Bussolotti et al., 2002). Also, it was found that perception of self and family cohesion levels increase when monthly income decrease. The findings are supported by studies that found that low income had no effect on family cohesion (Kim et al., 2015) and showed that psychological resilience is independent of income (Wingo et al., 2010).

Conclusion and Discussion

As a result of the hypothesis tests in the study, it was determined that emotional eating decreased as self-perception, future perception, and social resources increased. The studies explaining the relationship between self-perception and eating disorders (Hy-mowitz et al., 2017) and research findings relating perception of self (Bekker et al., 2004), perception of future and social resources increase, when emotional eating decrease (Cecchetto et al., 2021; Altheimer & Urry, 2019; Benard et al., 2018) supports this finding. In addition, some studies found that work stress in the hotel sector increases emotional eating (Okumus et al., 2019).The hypotheses that increased family cohesion and social competence reduce emotional eating were rejected. This finding can be explained by the fact that individuals may increase the act of eating in social environments (Herman, 2017). On the other hand, there are studies that family cohesion positively effects intuitive eating, a type of emotional eating, and social competence

Theoretical Implications

As a result of the study, determining the effect of some variables related to psychological resilience on emotional eating offers opportunities for gastronomy and tourism researchers to investigate related variables in different sectors and businesses of tourism. Examining psychological resilience and emotional eating with qualitative research methods, especially in sectors where employees are exposed to food, such as the food and beverage sector, will reveal studies that can increase data diversity. Whether individuals with high self-perception, future perception and social resources are less likely to have different eating disorders compared to other individuals constitutes new research problems for the fields of psychology, tourism, gastronomy and nutrition. Comparing the results of studies investigating the relationship between psychological resilience and eating disorders reveals contributions that will benefit the development of literature in the field of psychology, tourism, gastronomy and nutrition.

Investigating the tendency of employees to eating disorders in terms of different psychological variables reveals new research topics that should be examined in hotels and different sectors. In addition, considering the studies showing that psychological resilience positively affects performance and job satisfaction (Hou et al., 2020), examining the relationship between psychological resilience, eating disorders, job performance and satisfaction variables creates new research problems.

Practical Implications

This study shows that some variables of psychological resilience affect emotional eating. Considering that eating disorders alternately negatively affect both psychology and psychological resilience (Zhang et al., 2021), the study will be able to contribute to the psychological and physical health of employees with the measures that can be taken by hotel and tourism managers. The fact that psychological resilience positively affects the performance and job satisfaction of tourism sector employees (Prayag et al., 2020) reveals that creating recreation areas for physical and mental relaxation for employees and serving healthy snacks in these areas can also contribute to service quality. The promotion and certification of healthy eating and physical relaxation facilities, which are hardly offered for employees in hotels and other tourism businesses, reveal the responsibilities of the authorities in the field of hotels and tourism. The spread of businesses of this nature may create opportunities related to tourism managements in terms of hiring more qualified personnel or ensuring employee satisfaction.

Limitations and suggestions

The study was conducted only for the employees of four-star and five-star hotels operating in Istanbul. The relationship between psychological resilience and emotional eating should be examined in different destinations and other employees in the tourism sector such as food and beverage workers, and chefs, tourist guides. On the other hand, quantitative research methods were used in the study and psychological resilience and emotional eating were determined as a result of the answers given by individuals. The relevant variables should be measured in studies using qualitative research methods such as observation and in-depth interviews.

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